

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING LEADERSHIP QUALITIES IN EDUCATION MANAGERS

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Abstract. *In this article leadership, leadership in education, leadership characteristics in educational managers, vision (vision and planning, motivation and inspiration, team building, decision making and responsibility, communication and listening skills, innovation and adaptation to change is covered extensively.*

Keywords: *leadership, educational leadership, leadership qualities in educational managers, vision (vision and planning, motivation and inspiration, team building, decision-making and responsibility, communication and listening skills, innovation and o'adapt to change.*

Introduction.

At present time in our republic, legal and regulatory frameworks have been established to develop leadership competencies in managerial personnel that meet the demands of the labor market. In the context of “Establishing a humane state by enhancing human dignity and further developing a free civil society” [1], the issue of scientifically studying the socio-psychological characteristics of developing leadership qualities in future leaders remains relevant.

In his book titled “Critical analysis, strict order and discipline, and personal responsibility must be the daily rule of every leader,” the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasizes:

“A leader must not only manage formal processes typical of certain periods of social influence within groups, but also have a clear understanding of goals and objectives. Only if they develop leadership qualities that contribute to the organization and do not shy away from responsibility, can they establish an effective work system.” [2]

Definitely, the effective functioning and development of the education system depend not only on the professional qualifications of teachers but also directly on the leadership potential of education managers. Education managers play an important role in managing educational processes, improving students’ academic performance, and ensuring the effective work of the pedagogical team. Their leadership qualities are a key factor in making important decisions within the organization and in achieving overall educational goals. From this perspective, the concept of leadership in education managers plays a vital role in organizing the effective functioning of the education system.

Certainly, leadership is the process of guiding a team toward a goal, inspiring them, and managing them. Education managers are individuals who lead within an organization, directing all participants—from teachers to students toward a common objective. A manager’s leadership ability has a direct impact on the success of the educational process.

Methodology.

The concept of leadership is applied in many fields, but in education, it is even more complex. In addition to their professional skills, education managers must possess pedagogical

and psychological knowledge. They must effectively exercise leadership in managing teachers, understanding students' needs, and improving the quality of education.

Since ancient times, the issue of leadership has been studied, where the need to find a protector or savior (tribal elders, clan leaders) was tied to historical models of leadership. This was often reflected in the biographies of prophets such as Jesus, Muhammad, and Buddha. The impact of historical development on human consciousness has altered approaches to leadership and has found its place in modern management [3].

It is known to everyone that leadership does not have a precise definition for every situation. This explains the multifaceted nature of leadership, the existence of various approaches to analyzing it, as well as common misconceptions about it. In general (for various spheres of human activity), leadership refers to a particular individual's status or position within a group or society at large, and their ability to influence others guiding their efforts toward achieving specific goals. [4]

Moreover, leadership is the art and practice of guiding others, motivating and inspiring them on the path to achieving goals. Leadership is not just about managing a team; it also involves helping others develop their best abilities, providing them with the necessary resources, and ensuring collaborative efforts toward a shared objective.

The issue of studying the personality of a leader in management has been a significant matter in all eras of human society. The main reason for this is, firstly, that social relations in every era have necessitated someone occupying a high position in society; and secondly, people's way of life, development, well-being, and ability to live a happy life have depended on that individual in a high position on their various virtues and traits [5].

Results and discussion.

What is more important, the concept of leadership in education managers is primarily associated with the effective management of the educational process, motivating students and teachers, making decisions necessary to achieve organizational goals, and managing the team. Such leadership is essential for creating a successful learning environment in educational institutions.

As leaders, education managers must possess the following socio-psychological characteristics:

1. Vision (Foresight and Planning):

An education manager must be able to foresee the future and develop clear strategies to improve the educational process. They should define the goals of the educational institution and work collaboratively with students, teachers, and parents to achieve these goals.

2. Motivation and Inspiration:

To encourage teachers and students and help them achieve their best results, the education manager must convey confidence and positive energy to others. They play a key role in motivating their team toward success.

3. Team Building:

Education managers must establish good relationships with teachers, administrative staff, and parents, and work effectively with them. This, in turn, helps unite all participants toward a common goal.

4. Decision-Making and Responsibility:

As a leader, the manager must make important decisions to ensure the effective functioning of the educational institution. They must be ready to take responsibility in any situation.

5. Communication and Listening Skills:

Managers must establish effective communication with their staff, students, and parents. This is important not only for solving problems but also for understanding the needs of team members and providing support.

6. Innovation and Adaptability to Change:

Education managers must be ready to accept innovations and changes. By adopting innovative approaches, using technologies, and updating teaching methods, managers can improve the quality of education.

Thus, the concept of leadership in education managers is viewed not only as a means of achieving goals but also as an activity that serves the development of educational institutions, inspires and supports students and the teaching staff.

The presence of leadership in education managers directly impacts the quality of the educational process, the professional development of teachers, and the success of students. Through effective leadership, managers can help teachers enhance their skills, unite the team, and increase the overall efficiency of the educational institution. The influence of leadership increases teachers' motivation and dedication to their work, which, in turn, raises students' achievements in the learning process.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the concept of leadership in education managers occupies a central place in the effective functioning of the education system. A high level of leadership positively shapes the internal environment of educational institutions, directs teachers and students toward goals, and improves the overall quality of education. Developing the leadership potential of education managers contributes to their success in managing their teams and organizing the educational process effectively. Therefore, studying and developing the leadership skills of education managers serves the future success of the education system.

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